

SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTS FOR MECHANICAL PROPERTIES DOMINATING THE PRESS MOLDING USING CFRTP PREFORMS

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ABSTRACT

The press molding using carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) attracts attention to reduce product processing times of CFRP. In the press molding, draping ability can be improved by preforming, and preforming without defects is required for making high quality products. Then, the present paper examined the pull-out property and shear property of CFRTP preforms made of prepreg or semipreg, which dominate press molding, by experiments, and made models for CFRTP preforming simulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

High production rates are required to apply carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) to automotive industry. One method for reducing product processing times is the press molding using carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP). In this method, draping ability can be improved by preforming at the temperature which is higher than the glass transition temperature. However, in this preforming process, some defects such as gaps, tape slippage or wrinkles are generated, and they become reduction factors of the product's in-service performance. Reduction of defects can be achieved by optimizing the geometrical and constraint conditions of preforming process using an accurate numerical prediction.

This paper evaluates pull-out and shear properties of CFRTP preforms, which are essential for drape simulations [1, 2, 3]. First, pull-out and picture-frame tests were carried out, and then simulations were conducted to assess their predictive capabilities.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Specimens

Two tape materials were considered in this study. Both materials consisted of TR50S and DIAMIRON C, and they were cut into strips. TR50S and DIAMIRON C were uni-directional carbon fibers and a polyamide 6 single-layer film, respectively, and manufactured by MITSUBISHI CHEMICAL. One material was a prepreg, and the other was a semipreg. In the prepreg, the thermoplastic resin film was laminated to the reinforcement. The prepreg was very thin, and manufactured by Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture. In the semipreg, the thermoplastic resin film was laminated to the reinforcement without fully impregnating the fibers. The semipreg was manufactured by MITSUYA. The material properties are listed in Table 1. Two kinds of specimens were made by the two materials respectively as shown in Fig. 1. This configuration is one type of AP-PLY (Advanced Placed Ply) that combines through-the-thickness reinforcements with an automated fiber placement process [4].

	Carbon fiber	Matrix	V_f [%]	Nominal thickness [μm]	Width [mm]
Prepreg	TR50S	PA6	53.4	43	10
Semipreg	TR50S	PA6	37	64	10

Table 1: Material properties of prepreg and semipreg tapes

Fig. 1 Procedure to make an AP-PLY pattern

2.2 Pull-out test

Tool-ply friction and ply-ply friction were measured using pull-out tests in a tensile machine having a thermostat, referred to the literature [5]. In this test, sandpapers were adhered to the upper and bilateral edges of specimens to prevent tapes from moving over. Fig. 2 showed a setup of this experiment. First, the specimen was clamped between two aluminum plates. PTFE (polytetrafluoroethylene) sheets were inserted between these plates and the specimen. Then a normal load was applied by tightening a screw and measured by a load cell. Finally, fixing horizontal tapes, vertical tapes were pulled out. The thermostat temperature was kept at 423 K, and a thermocouple was attached to the specimen. Load-displacement relations and temperature of specimens were measured. The pull-out speed was 30 mm/min.

Fig. 2 Appearance of pull-out test: (a) before the test and (b) after the test

The temperature of the specimens was around 400 K during this test. This value was between the glass transition point (320 K) and the melting point (498 K) of PA6. Fig. 3 shows the relationship between pull-out load and the pull-out displacement. Typically, the friction force reached the peak value at an initial stage, and then it became an almost constant force. Ply-ply friction coefficient μ_{pp} , and tool-ply friction coefficient μ_{tp} are related to the pull-out load F_p and the normal load F_n :

$$(\mu_{pp} + \mu_{tp})F_n = F_p \quad (1)$$

To determine the friction coefficients, another pull-out test was conducted without horizontal tapes, and tool-ply friction was measured [6, 7]. In this test, μ_{tp} is defined as:

$$\mu_{tp} = \frac{F_p}{2F_n} \quad (2)$$

Then, the friction coefficients were obtained, and listed in Table 2. Tool-ply friction coefficients were measured twice, and the results had a large variation. It was concluded that there was no clear difference confirmed between the friction coefficients of two materials.

Fig. 3 Load-displacement relations in pull-out tests

	Prepreg A	Prepreg B	Semipreg A	Semipreg B
Ply-ply friction coefficient	0.031	0.031	0.063	0.063
Tool-ply friction coefficient	0.17	0.087	0.12	0.076

Table 2: Friction coefficients of prepregs and semipregs

2.3 Picture-frame test

The picture-frame test provides information on the response of preforms to shear deformation [8]. Using this test method, uniform shear deformation state of the majority of the specimen is achieved. The bundle directions were aligned with the frame and the upper crosshead moved with a speed of 30 mm/min in the vertical direction using the same testing machine as in pull-out tests. The initial contact area of two tapes was 1,600 mm². In the tests, bundle edges were free to rotate using pins. The specimen was positioned between two aluminum plates which were separated by about 0.32 mm to keep the specimen configuration during the shear deformation. In the same procedure as in pull-out tests, a thermocouple was attached to the specimen, and the thermostat temperature was kept at 423 K.

Fig. 4 shows the specimen before and after the test. The angle of the frame θ is calculated as:

$$\cos \theta = \frac{\sqrt{2}L + d}{2L} \quad (3)$$

where L is the frame length, and d is the measured vertical displacement. The shear angle γ is related to the angle of the frame θ as:

$$\gamma = 90 - 2\theta \quad (4)$$

The shear force F_s is calculated from the angle of the frame θ , the measured pull-out load F_p and the offset load F_o as:

$$F_s = \frac{F_p - F_o}{2 \cos \theta} \quad (5)$$

The offset force F_0 is the force required to deform the frame, and was measured the picture-frame test without a specimen.

Fig. 5 shows the relationship between shear force and the shear angle. The shear stiffness increased with increasing shear angle. In the semipreg specimen, the shear load increased sharply with the angle at 6° and 28° because of contact failure. In this test, specimens were not deformed with the shear angle over 30° due to the interference of the jigs. The improvement of the jigs is necessary to deform with the angle over 30° in order to observe the shear locking of the specimen.

Fig. 4 Appearance of a picture-frame test: (a)before the test and (b)after the test

Fig. 5 Load-angle relations in picture-frame tests

3 SIMULATION

Simulations were based on finite element method using a commercial dynamic explicit analysis software LS-DYNA.

3.1 Pull-out simulation

The model for a pull-out simulation is shown in Fig. 6. This reproduced the configuration of pull-out specimens. Four-node rectangular shell elements were used. Each vertical and horizontal tape was discretized with 10,400 and 4,400 elements, respectively. The sandpapers and aluminum plates were modeled as rigid surfaces, containing 5,200 elements. The total number of elements was 123,600. Each tape was assumed as a transversely isotropic and elastic material. The parameters of this model are given in Table 3. The subscripts 1, 2 and 3 are used to denote the direction parallel to the fibers, transverse and thickness directions, respectively. In the simulation, a friction coefficients and normal loads were determined so as to reproduce the pull-out tests of prepreg A and semipreg A. Vertical tapes were

constrained to an upper rigid plate A, and horizontal tapes were constrained to bilateral rigid plates B and C.

A pull-out simulation was carried out by two steps. In step 1, in order to apply a normal pressure to the tapes, two rigid plates D and E were displaced against each other. In step 2, the upper rigid plate A was displaced upwards with vertical tapes at a rate of 1,000 mm/s, while a constant normal load was applied to the rigid plate D and other rigid plates were constrained. The pull-out speed was made faster than actual test speed in order to decrease the CPU time for the simulation.

The simulated results are shown in Fig. 7. The curves typically showed an initial peak force, after which they approached an almost steady state as in pull-out tests. Although the initial peak force was larger than the value in the experiment, the magnitude of the steady load was similar to the experimental value, as shown in Fig. 8. Therefore, the present model could reproduce the frictional pull-out of the tapes in the specimen.

Fig. 6 Models of a pull-out simulation: before the pull-out (left) and after the pull-out (right)

	Prepreg	Semipreg
ρ [g/cm ³]	0.911	1.01
E_1 [GPa]	87.9	70.2
E_2, E_3 [GPa]	18.1	12.3
ν_{21}, ν_{31}	0.067	0.049
ν_{32}	0.44	0.44
G_{12}, G_{31} [GPa]	7.39	7.96
G_{23} [GPa]	6.30	4.28

Table 3: Material parameters used in simulations

Fig. 7 Load-displacement relations in pull-out simulations

Fig. 8 Comparison of pull-out tests and pull-out simulations

3.2 Shear simulation

In a shear simulation, shear deformation of AP-PLY was examined using different boundary condition from the experiment, because of the simplification of the simulation model. The model for a shear simulation is shown in Fig. 9. Four-node rectangular shell elements were used, and reproduced the configuration of AP-PLY. Each tape was discretized with 10,400 elements. The total number of elements was 372,880. Each tape was assumed as a transversely isotropic and elastic material. The simulation also used the parameters of this model listed in Table 3. The subscripts 1, 2 and 3 were used to denote the direction parallel to the fibers, transverse and thickness directions, respectively. Vertical tapes were constrained to upper and lower rigid plates F and G. Bilateral edges of horizontal tapes were fixed in space. The initial contact area of two tape models was 6,400 mm².

A shear simulation was also carried out by two steps. In step 1, in order to apply a normal pressure to the tapes, two rigid plates H and I were displaced against each other. In step 2, the upper and lower rigid plates F and G were rotated clockwise on a center of this model with vertical tapes at a rate of 17.5 rad/s, while a constant normal load was applied to the rigid plate H and the rigid plate I was constrained. The rotational speed was faster than the actual test to decrease the CPU time.

The simulated result is shown in Fig. 10. The shear load was unstable at an initial stage, because a contact force was not calculated stably. The constant normal load applied in step 2 was 1,000 N. The magnitude of the shear load calculated by the shear simulation could not be compared with that measured by picture-frame tests. However, the shear stiffness increased with increasing shear angle, as in picture-frame tests. The magnitude of shear load in simulations may be close to that in tests by changing the boundary condition. The friction between pins and a specimen or inaccurate offset load in the shear tests might lead to the difference in the initial rise of the shear loads between shear tests and simulations.

Fig. 9 Models of a shear simulation: before the shear (left), and after the shear (right)

Fig. 10 Load-angle relations in shear simulation

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present paper examined pull-out property and shear property of CFRTP preforms, which dominate press molding, by experiments, and made simulation models for CFRTP preforming. Two kinds of materials, prepreg and semipreg tapes, were considered.

First, pull-out tests and picture-frame tests were conducted. In the pull-out tests, fixing the horizontal tapes, the vertical tapes were pulled out, and friction coefficients between the tapes were measured. In the picture-frame tests, uniform shear deformation was applied to the specimen using a picture-frame, and the shear stiffness increased with increasing shear angle.

Second, simulation models were made using LS-DYNA, and their predictive capabilities were assessed. Using shell elements, each tape was modeled and the specimens were reproduced. In the pull-out simulations, pull-out load was calculated by the method similar to the pull-out test, and the magnitude of the steady pull-out load was similar to that in the experiments. In shear simulations, shear deformation was achieved by rotating the vertical tapes, and the shear stiffness increased with increasing shear angle, as in picture-frame tests.

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